

ADAPTATION TO DROUGHT/DELAYED RAINFALL IN RICE CULTIVATION, BIHAR, INDIA

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAU	Bihar Agriculture University
BRLPS	Bihar Rural Livelihoods Promotion Society
BRP	Block Resource Person
CLF	Cluster Level Federation
CRP	Community Resource Person (Jeevika)
CSISA	Cereal Systems Initiative for South Asia
DSR	Direct Seeded Rice
EGP	Eastern Gangetic Plains
EiA	Excellence in Agronomy
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
FPO	Farmer Producer Organisations
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IMD	India Meteorological Department
IRRI	International Rice Research Institute
JEEViKA	Women's Farmers Groups (Self-help groups promoted by BRLPS)
KCC	Kisan Credit Card
KVK	Krishi Vigyan Kendra
MVP	Minimum Viable Products
SHG	Self Help Groups
VO	Village Organisation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents findings from 21 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) conducted in seven districts of Bihar namely Muzaffarpur, Madhubani, Samastipur, Vaishali, Gaya, Nalanda, and Lakhisarai with 221 farmers 116 female and 105 males to establish a deeper understanding of the challenges and coping mechanisms in the rice-wheat system related to climate change variabilities faced by farmers in the region. The findings also highlight the opportunities and suggestive interventions for strengthening farmers capacities to deal with the challenges. The study was conducted as part of the Excellence in Agronomy (EiA) initiative use case on “Managing time in the rice-based cropping systems of South Asia”. FGDs were conducted with three groups of farmers in each of the seven districts: Demonstration or Demo farmers, non-Demo farmers and JEEViKA farmers to capture their varied perspectives on challenges and opportunities in rice-wheat cropping systems.

The findings present that the rice wheat cropping system is the dominant cropping systems across the districts where Rice in Kharif and Wheat in Rabi are the predominant crop. As far as the engagement of household members in agriculture is concerned, it was found that both men and women are involved in agriculture but with variations related to the degree of women’s active involvement based on farmer categories. For example, in the big farmers household no female members were involved in the agriculture operations on the field and on the other hand the involvement of female members of small and marginal farmers are quite common. In general children’s engagement in agriculture was found very limited and that too mainly carrying meals to the farm.

FGD captured the complex set of threats, risks and challenges faced by the farmers in the rice-wheat cropping systems. Unpredictable and unevenly distributed rainfall patterns were a major concern raised by the farmers for making decisions related to planting time. For instance, the late arrival of rainfall in 2022 led to a delay in transplanting, especially affecting the poor farmers with no irrigation facilities. During the discussion farmers also raised the concerns such as a) Tenant farmers working on leased lands were doubly disadvantaged in terms of access to borewells or other irrigation sources b.) High costs incurred in irrigation were a key deterrent for all kinds of farmers c) High cost in procuring diesel due to lack of adequate and regular supply of affordable power in irrigation. d) Increasing cost of irrigation due to scattered farmland.

Although irrigation was considered by the farmers as a possible solution to deal with unreliable weather and to do the planting when required.

In the subsequent discussion farmers shared the limited availability of finance to invest in agriculture as another concern. They shared the need for a formal, systematic, and timely institutional credit facilities in these areas. The lack of timely access to, and reliable information on, good quality and affordable farm inputs was another challenge mentioned by farmers. Unavailability of labour in the household and in the community, was considered by farmers as one of the critical challenges farmers faced during the sowing and transplanting period, and in the overall cropping cycle. Across the crop cycle stages and activities, a cross-cutting and persistent constraint that emerged was the lack of timely and reliable information and advisory services particularly related to monsoon. The lack of proper and reliable marketing facilities was also identified by the farmers as one of the challenges.

Farmers capacity to farm in general and to plant on time specifically, was influenced by a complex interplay of the climate-related and systemic barriers described above. Looking through an intersectional and gender lens it was found that farmers had similar yet differing experiences of being impacted with the multiple constraints facing the rice-wheat cropping systems. These varied interpretations were based on the socio-economic and demographic background of the farmers. For instance, landless or tenant farmers, women farmers with migrant husbands and resource-poor and marginalised farmers were in a more precarious situation in terms of their capacity to mitigate risks and complete their farm operations on time, make final decisions regarding transplanting dates, and sustain their agricultural productivity and growth. In the study sites, Demo farmers were found to be the farmers with more resources and better access to services and capital as compared to non-Demo and women farmers. During the FGDs it was found that the women farmers who were part of the JEEViKA did not raise concern accessing financial support, extension, and advisory services. They highlighted that being a member of self-help groups (SHGs) they get support in enhancing their access to reliable sources of finance, extension, and advisory services.

The report also presents evidence of coping mechanisms adopted by the farmers. Replanting the nursery in case of delayed rainfall and low germination was one of the important coping mechanisms mentioned by the farmers. To deal with the rainfall uncertainties many farmers mentioned that constructing borewell at individual level or renting in the borewell services are the popular mitigation strategies. The community level engagement to mitigate the risk was highlighted by very few FGDs. Instances of community innovation emerged from some sites wherein male farmers collectively constructed borewells to irrigate on time and women farmers raised nurseries collectively to manage limited water resources. During the women farmers group FGD, the expansion of farmers individual and collective capacity by extension and support system of SHGs/Jeevika came out as one of the strong platforms to deal with the management practices and its associated risk in the rice-wheat cropping farming system.

Farmer groups across the districts reported facing a delay in transplanting in 2022, primarily reported to be caused by the late arrival of rainfall. Farmers with irrigation facilities prepared the nurseries in Rohini (May 25-June 8) or Mrigashira (June 8-June 20), and the farmers who had limited access to irrigation through renting waited for their chance and prepared nurseries in Mrigashira. The timeline of seeding also depends on the seed variety. For instance, open pollinated varieties (opv) varieties were sown in Rohini Nakshatra (May 25-June 8) while hybrid varieties which is relatively shorter in duration, was sown in Ardra Nakshatra (June 22-July 5). Farmers with no access to any irrigation source waited for the rainfall to even prepare the nursery which caused them further delays in the transplanting. A delay in rainfall caused a drought-like situation and raised the temperature limiting the germination of seeds in the nurseries. Many farmer groups reported reduced yield and wastage of financial capital in farm inputs which was lost due to delays in rainfall in the year 2022.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Climate change and associated uncertainties, particularly related to rainfall have serious direct and indirect consequences on cropping systems, particularly on planting dates and the resultant crop production and food security situation of the agriculture-dependent farming communities (Park et al., 2018). Other climate change-induced vulnerabilities facing agriculture are changes in average temperatures, weather extremes, pests and diseases, and changes in the nutritional quality of foods (Tesfaye et al., 2017). Evidence suggests that these vulnerabilities and weather extremes in the form of erratic monsoons and increased frequency and intensity of drought and flooding are expected to further impact agriculture in many ways (Chattopadhyay, 2011; Randhawa et al., 2014). Agriculture in South Asia is highly susceptible to climate variability and is more likely to have a direct impact on the livelihoods of millions of farmers in the region, particularly the small and marginal landholders (Aryal et al., 2020). Indo Gangetic Plain is the main wheat growing area of the South Asia, with rice wheat cropping system (Andrew et al.2022). In India, and more specifically in the eastern part of the country, 80% of the rice-growing areas are rain-fed and thus suffer either from excess water or from drought depending upon rainfall pattern (ibid).

Agriculture contributes 21.3% of Bihar's GDP (GOB, 2015). Lying in the eastern part of the country, Bihar is one of the climate-sensitive states of India due to its topography, its susceptibility to hydro-meteorological natural disasters and a high proportion of its rural communities living in disadvantage and abject poverty (ibid). The state of Bihar falls under the Eastern Gangetic Plains (EGP) characterised by high rainfall region with recurring floods, but the occurrence of droughts during the monsoon season is also a serious concern threatening farmers' productivity (Subash et al., 2012). Since rice and wheat crops are important Kharif (monsoon) and Rabi (winter) crops respectively in the state, a lack of awareness of rainfall timings and the occurrence of droughts and floods can lead to a delay in planting and endanger crop yields. Moreover, this uncertainty increases the dependence of farming communities in Eastern Gangetic Plains (EGP) on irrigation, primarily through groundwater, which is in a precarious condition in the state, owing to the scarce, unreliable, and expensive irrigational infrastructure and declining water table. (Sinha et al., 2017; Urfels et al., 2023). Research over the last decades has shown that effective management of the cropping calendar through timely planting is a precondition for achieving regional food security in the EGP and building resilient agroecosystems (Urfels et al., 2021).

Timely crop planting and harvesting are linked to high and stable levels of crop productivity and overall agricultural development as they align crop cycles with favourable climatic conditions thereby mitigating risks of crop losses and increasing resource-use efficiencies (Singh et al., 2019). However, more than 50% of farmers are small landholders in eastern India (EiA Brief, 2023). The vulnerability context of the farmers and other socio-economic factors influence farmer's decisions to plant crops during an optimal time window. With lower levels of literacy and mobility, and unequal access and exposure to modern and improved technological innovations, women and marginalised farmers are in a more vulnerable situation in terms of making decisions on the farm (Agarwal et al., 2022). With an aim to support small and marginal farmers to adapt to the impacts of climate change and specially to address the delay in planting, the Excellence in Agronomy (EiA) initiative is working in the region on developing a dynamic gender-inclusive and data-driven tool to empower farmers to make informed decisions about timely planting for rice. In order to understand the coping mechanisms related to climate change and variabilities and opportunities that can be built upon to strengthen farmer capacities for timely planting, improved agriculture productivity and enhance farm incomes a study was conducted in seven districts of Bihar.

1.1 Research objective

Pivoted on the context that more than 50% of the farmers in eastern India plant rice and wheat late. If timely planting is done it can double productivity in the region and reduce vulnerability to seasonal drought in rice and terminal heat in wheat. A prototype of demand-driven spatially explicit planting date advisory to optimise resource use and improve profitability by addressing landscape heterogeneity, monsoon variability, and risks of innovations in rice-wheat systems is being created in the ongoing planting date use case in Bihar.

In realm of the current situation, this study was designed to understand and delve deeper into the farmers' adaptation to the climate change and drought-like situation they faced and their coping mechanisms. It thus becomes crucial to delve deeper and understand farmers' perspective on the barriers opportunities and possible interventions needed to accelerate the pace of timely planting.

Following thematic areas were explored to understand the research objective from farmers perspective.

i) Perceptions of threats in rice-wheat cropping systems,
ii) Rice transplanting date scenarios,
iii) Drought/flood situation in the respective villages and their coping mechanism,
iv) Constraints and issues with respect to nursery establishments and transplanting,
v) Wheat cropping in the upcoming season and,
vi) Agro-advisory systems in the region.

CHAPTER 2: RESEARCH DESIGN

2.1 Study context

Twenty-one Focus Group discussions (FGDs) were held in 2022-2023 in the 7 districts of Bihar namely, Madhubani, Muzaffarpur, Vaishali, Samastipur, Nalanda, Gaya and Lakhisarai with farmers. These seven districts fall under two Agro-climatic zones. Muzaffarpur, Madhubani, Samastipur and Vaishali are in Agro-climatic zone 1, also called the northwest alluvial plains characterised by an average annual rainfall of 1234.7 mm, medium acidic, heavy textured and sandy loam to clayed soil, and large areas remaining underwater (flood-prone). Gaya, Nalanda and Lakhisarai on the other hand are in southeast alluvial plains or Agro-climatic zone 3, witnessing 1102.1 mm of average annual rainfall and made up of old alluvium to sandy loam soils (ParthSarathi & Singh, 2013).

The purpose of the FGDs was to understand the perceptions on threats in rice-wheat cropping systems, rice transplanting date scenarios, drought/flood situation in the respective villages and their coping mechanism, constraints and issues concerning nursey establishments and transplanting, wheat cropping in the upcoming season and agro-advisory systems in the region.

2.2 Sample design

FGDs were conducted with three categories or groups of farmers in each of the seven districts:

1. Demonstration farmers: Farmers on whose plots the EiA trials have been set up.
2. Non–Demo farmers: Farmers of the same area where the Demonstration was not done.
3. Women Farmers Group: Women farmers of the same block who are members of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) promoted by JEEViKA, Bihar Rural Livelihoods Promotion Society (BRLPs)

Sampling strategy: At the core of the sample selection were the Demo farmers– In each district, all Demo farmers (from different blocks in the district) were requested to travel to one of the villages that were logistically convenient for all to participate in the FGD. Hence Demo groups FGDs include men and women farmers from different villages. To draw a comparison, non-Demo farmers (men and women) were selected from the same village where the Demo group FGD was conducted. To understand the challenges and opportunities through a gender lens, Jeevika farmers were also included in the study from the same area. SHG and Village Organisation (VO) members from the same block (and different villages) were assembled for the FGD. For non-Demo groups’ FGDs and Jeevika groups’ FGDs– participants were randomly selected. The goal of the sampling strategy was to select respondents who were willing to share their experiences and perspectives and provide rich insights into the areas of inquiry. **Table 1 presents the sample design of the FGDs with 21 farmer groups across the three categories in 7 districts.**

Table 1: Sample Design

Participant category	Participant Sex	Muzaffar pur	Madhubani	Samastipur	Vaishali	Gaya	Nalanda	Lakhisarai	TOTAL
Demo	Women	2	1	0	0	0	4	0	7
	Men	6	8	8	8	8	5	9	52
Non -Demo	Men	10	9	3	5	7	9	11	54
	Women	0	2	5	9	5	1	0	22
Jeevika	Women	12	12	12	14	12	12	12	86
	Men	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
TOTAL FGD PARTICIPANTS = 221 (115 Women; 106 Men)									

2.3 Data collection

The FGDs were conducted between October to November 2022 and were designed as semi-structured interactions, with probes that were structured around the research aim and objectives. FGD guides were written in English and administered in Hindi or other local languages by the interviewers. FGD was audio-recorded after obtaining informed verbal and written consent from the participants.

2.4 Data analysis

FGD recordings were originally in Hindi and were translated and transcribed into English. A total of 21 FGDs, (7 in each of the three-farmer category/3 in each of the 7 districts) were entered into a data template designed to record the responses. Thematic content analysis was done in two phases: The first phase of data analysis involved screening the transcript texts for descriptive codes or common areas of information. Recurring themes were identified afterwards followed by the second phase of comparing responses across farmer groups and the seven districts.

CHAPTER 3: FINDINGS FROM FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS (FGDs)

This section is structured based on the integration of the initial hypothesis and areas of inquiry set out before conducting the FGDs and the perspectives and insights that emerged from them. The findings are presented in five broad themes and various sub-themes under each of the themes, outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: Themes and sub-themes of the findings

1.	Cropping systems <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Major cropping system➤ Role of household members in agriculture
2.	Major threats and challenges in rice-wheat cropping systems. <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Major risks in rice-wheat cropping system in the past 5 years (2018-2022)➤ Constraints and challenges specific to nursery establishment➤ Drought and Flood situation in the village in 2022➤ Challenges due to drought and flood situation in 2022➤ Anticipated challenges in the wheat cropping in the coming season (Rabi 2022-23)
3.	Rice planting and transplanting dates scenario <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Timeline-related scenario facts in rice cultivation➤ Common methods of planting are sowing and transplanting.➤ Decision-making on transplanting dates
4.	Coping mechanism to manage drought and flood situations in agriculture. <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Solutions adopted to address rainfall-timing-related challenges.➤ Support required to implement solutions in nursery & transplanting
5.	Agro-advisory system <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Sources of information and barriers to information➤ Thematic areas covered and farmers' perception and use of info.➤ Ways of improving current advisory systems (Thematic areas anticipated, platforms, timeline, language)

3.1 Cropping systems

3.1.1 Major cropping systems

Cropping patterns are influenced by biophysical factors such as agro-climatic zones, or the topography, temperature, rainfall and soil properties of the region; infrastructural factors such as agriculture innovation, technology, and irrigation sources; political and economic factors such as market situation (food prices and volatility), larger trade trends and government policies; socio-cultural factors such as norms and culture; or demographic factors such as population growth, migration and forced displacement.¹

Rice in Kharif and wheat in Rabi are found to be the predominant cropping system in the region followed by maize, vegetables and pulses in small patches of the area as per farmers need. Following are the cropping patterns followed in the 7 districts. Table 3 presents an overview of the major crops grown in two primary agricultural seasons: kharif and rabi, and the farmer-reported land distribution between the crops grown.

In **Muzaffarpur**, the major crops grown in the Kharif season are rice in the lowlands and pulses and mustard in the upper lands. During the Rabi season, wheat is a primary crop and maize is grown as a secondary crop. Though the cropping pattern was similar across the three farmer groups (Demo, non-Demo and Jeevika) who participated in the FGDs, the Demo and non-Demo groups reported growing primarily rice in Kharif season while the Jeevika farmers also grew mustard and pulses and cultivated rice in their uplands besides the traditional practice of cultivating rice majorly in lowlands.

In **Madhubani**, farmers across the three groups reported growing rice in Kharif with a few patches of vegetables for self-consumption. Similarly, in the Rabi season, wheat is planted as a major crop, and potatoes and pulses are planted in 5-25% of the available lands. Demo farmers shared that one-fourth of their lands remain fallow after paddy harvest.

Farmers in **Samastipur** also rely on rice as their major crop in the Kharif season. The non-Demo farmers, however, reported that rice is not considered a primary crop in their village and that it is grown only in 30% of their lands. Instead, sugarcane is sowed after paddy harvest and grown as a year-long crop. In the Rabi season, non-Demo farmers grow wheat in half their lands while the other half is occupied by the sugarcane crop. Demo farmers and Jeevika farmers also cultivate wheat as a primary crop, but while Demo farmers distribute lands in the ratio of 75:25 for wheat, and, pulses and vegetables, Jeevika farmers grow maize and potatoes in half their lands, after dedicating the other half to wheat crops.

Vaishali district farmers also reported rice and wheat as their major crops in the Kharif and Rabi seasons respectively. All three groups of farmers grow vegetables in small patches for self-consumption during Kharif. In Rabi, in addition to wheat in half to one-third of their lands, farmers grow maize, pulses, potatoes and vegetables.

Farmers in **Gaya** cultivate rice in the lowlands and vegetables in the uplands. Vegetables in Kharif are mostly grown for self-consumption and surplus produce is sold locally. In the Rabi season, wheat is grown in large patches and other crops such as pulses such as chickpeas, red gram, mustard, onion, tomatoes, and other vegetables are grown.

¹ Factors' terminology adapted from drivers of food systems from the conceptual framework of sustainable food systems developed by HLPE at the FAO, 2017.

In **Nalanda**, Demo and Jeevika farmers reported growing predominantly rice crops in the Kharif season. The non-Demo farmers on the other hand, grow vegetables in almost half of their lands, and rice in the other half. All farmer groups grow wheat in Rabi and pulses such as chickpeas and vegetables in small patches of irrigated lands.

Lakhisarai farmers grow rice in most of their lands, particularly lowlands, and vegetables in 10-25% of their lands. non-Demo farmers reported growing only rice. In Rabi, wheat was grown in half to one-third of farmers' lands across the groups and pulses, maize, and vegetables in the remaining lands.

Table 3: Overview of major crops grown in the seven districts.

District	Kharif Season Crops planted: Land distribution	Rabi season Crops planted: Land distribution
Muzaffarpur	Rice: 90% Pulses, Mustard: 10 % (Jeevika farmers)	Wheat: 75% Maize: 25%
Madhubani	Rice: 90%	Wheat: 75-95% Potatoes, Pulses: 5-25%
Samastipur	Rice: 90%	Wheat: 50-75% Maize, Potatoes, Sugarcane: 25-50%
Vaishali	Rice: 80-90% Vegetables: 10-20%	Wheat: 50-75% Maize, Potatoes, Vegetables: 20-25%
Gaya	Rice: 75-90% Vegetables: 10-25%	Wheat: 75-80% Pulses, Onions, Mustard: 20-25%
Nalanda	Rice: 80-90%	Wheat: 75-90% Pulses, Vegetables: 10-25%
Lakhisarai	Rice: 75-90% Vegetables: 10-25%	Wheat: 50-75% Pulses, Vegetables, Maize: 25-50%

3.1.2 Role of household members in agriculture

Family income and social status show an influence on gender roles and responsibilities both in households and farming activities. All the farmers shared about both women's and men's involvement in agriculture but with variations related to the degree of women's active involvement based on farmer categories and locations. For instance, the Demo farmers from Gaya, Vaishali, Lakhisarai and Muzaffarpur described that women of their families do not work on the farm instead they employed poor and landless women farmers as agricultural labourers. FGDs with the remaining farmer groups reported equal participation of men and women in the farm. Non-Demo farmers from Gaya and Madhubani mentioned that "all adult household members work on the farm due to labour shortage." In contrast to Demo farmers who reported restricted women's mobility, Jeevika farmers reported a high participation of women in agriculture. Moreover, women from locations with high rates of male out-migration for work reported more substantial participation of women on the farm. Jeevika farmers from Nalanda remarked, **"How will men farm without women? Men hardly stay here, and it is women who take care of the farm."**

➤ **The Gendered Division of labour**

The dominant patriarchal rules and norms are well reflected in the process of socialisation. As far as the distribution of farm roles between men and women is concerned, normative and gendered division of labour emerged across all groups, particularly from the Jeevika farmers who were more articulate about the defined gender roles. Work done by men on the farm was typically described as one requiring physical strength such as ploughing, tilling and irrigation. Women were reported to be engaged in work involving drudgeries such as managing plant nurseries, transplanting, weeding, harvesting and post-harvest activities such as threshing (paddy), cleaning and drying the crop. One of the Jeevika farmers from Nalanda shared her perception of women's role in agriculture, “Women do a lot in agriculture. Much more than men do. For example, we lay water pipes in the field for irrigation too and can fold them back.”

Mostly men were found to be involved in outward-facing work such as crop sales in the local markets and purchasing farm inputs. However, increasing male out-migration was reported as one of the emerging factors contributing to the changing gender division of labour shifting farm responsibilities to women. For instance, farmers from Madhubani, Samastipur, revealed that the roles of men and women in agriculture have started shifting in their area now. Due to the migration of the male spouse and other male members of the family women are being engaged more in various stages of farm operation which was not the case earlier. Women farmers of Jeevika from Muzaffarpur reported visiting the market for purchase and sale when men in their families out-migrate for work.

Children's education was prioritised and their involvement on the farm was limited to carrying food, water, and farm tools just as a supporting activity. Varied responses on the engagement of children on the farm were recorded, primarily influenced by the socio-economic characteristics of the household or the community. The majority of Demo and non-Demo farmers reported that it was rare for children to be involved in agriculture as they were busy with their studies. Moreover, farmers expressed their disinterest in “How is farming linked to children? We are already suffering as farmers. Why would we include our children? They should have a job”, commented a Demo farmer (M) from Gaya. Another dominant narrative on children's engagement in agriculture was that it is limited to bringing food and water to the farm or aiding in carrying pipes and other tools to the farm. In contrast, Jeevika farmers from Samastipur, Madhubani pointed to the children's involvement in activities such as ploughing, transplanting, and harvesting primarily driven by the absence of migrant male spouses. “During the transplanting or harvesting season, children also contribute, especially when our husbands are staying out for work. Or, children will take the food, and take care of the cow and other livestock.” But it was just an activity which was supportive in nature. It was not affecting the education of the children of the household. In other districts, farmers categorically mentioned that they did not want their children to engage in agricultural activities and instead focus on their studies.

3.2 Major threats and challenges facing rice-wheat cropping systems.

It is important to understand the challenges faced by farmers to develop strategies and coping mechanism from a bottom to top approach, putting this into context, it was further explored with the farmers about their experience and perspective on the major issues they faced in the rice-wheat cropping system in the last five years. The major challenge faced by the farmers in all districts was erratic and insufficient rainfall further exacerbated by the lack of irrigation sources.

3.2.1 Major threats in the rice-wheat cropping systems in the last 5 years (2018-2022)

The complex web of emerging threats, risks and challenges facing the rice-wheat cropping systems in the past year have been grouped into the following areas based on farmers' responses:

Major thematic dimensions of the issues faced by farmers emerged. related to **Physical, Human, Financial and Informational**

Climate variabilities; lack of irrigation facilities; labour unavailability, lack of access to good quality farm inputs; lack of financial capital, pests, and diseases; lack of access to systematic marketing facilities; and lack of information on new technologies/innovation an extension service (Figure 1). The farmers groups responses across the three respondents' groups of demo, non-demo and women farmers were related to the major threats and challenges were found to vary in degree as far as their perception was concerned (Figure .2)

Figure 1: Major threats in rice-wheat cropping systems

I. CLIMATE VARIABILITIES

Erratic monsoon and irregular rainfall were perceived as the critical challenges perceived and faced by farmers in the past years.

Farmers from across the three groups in the seven districts reported suffering from the unpredictability and the consecutive years of low and erratic rainfall forcing them to take risks and endure hardship in farming, Farmers used terms like “hope”, “luck” and “god’s grace” while describing their helplessness in agriculture due to high dependence on monsoon rainfall.

Rainfall was reported as an important determinant for making crop decisions. Several farmers across districts pointed to their **lack of awareness, capacity, and preparedness to deal with the erratic nature of rainfall further limiting their decision-making on planting timings**. Farmers indicated the occurrence of both drought/delayed rainfall and waterlogging in the last five years, making it riskier for them to make decisions on planting dates. The following quotes highlight the lack of preparedness for weather conditions and associated vulnerabilities faced by farmers.

Farmers from Muzaffarpur, Madhubani and Vaishali perceived themselves as more susceptible

“We don’t know when what will happen. We farmers calculate based on stars/ Nakshatra, but it is all changing nowadays, and we don’t know when to do what.” –Demo farmers (M), Muzaffarpur

“If we knew in advance that there would be no rain, we would not have planted such expensive seeds.”

–Non-Demo farmers (M), Gaya

“High temperature destroys our crops and these years just before harvest Paddy it rains heavily. It doesn’t rain when we need it to rain!”

–Jeevika farmers (F), Madhubani

to excessive waterlogging (flood-like situation) and adversities caused by it as their villages lie in and around the banks of Gandak and Bagmati rivers.

II. LACK OF IRRIGATION FACILITIES

In the context of low and unpredictable rainfall, irrigation becomes important to sustain crop growth and enhance crop yield. However, across the farmer groups, a **lack of reliable irrigation facilities and irregular access to irrigation sources** emerged as another issue. Borewells were reported as the primary source of irrigation for farmers in these regions. Motors/Pump-sets run by diesel or electricity are used to draw water from these borewells. However, borewells were constructed by farmers with better financial capital while the poorer farmers reported renting motors from the former. Farmers **without a borewell facility of their own perceived themselves to be more vulnerable** than the others. Some of the male non-Demo farmers in the Muzaffarpur FGD echoed, **“Those who have borewells manage somehow. Farmers without borewells suffer.”** Many other farmers from Vaishali and Lakhisarai shared a similar perspective. Though few anecdotes of farmers collectively constructing a borewell emerged from Lakhisarai, Madhubani and Nalanda, but **collective investments for borewell construction were perceived to be difficult due to the obscurity of operational structure and in the day-to-day functioning of wells leading to a lack of trust and confidence among farmers** in adopting a collective approach.

“Those of us who farm on leased lands can’t construct a borewell in that. The landlord doesn’t do it for us and does not allow us to do it. Also, if we invest in somebody else’s land, it will be our loss only”.

– Jeevika Farmers (F), Lakhisarai

The following perspectives describe the complex aspects of the challenges faced by farmers in relation to irrigation:

- a) **Tenant farmers working on leased lands were doubly disadvantaged in terms of access to borewells or other irrigation sources.** Farmers especially from Samastipur, Nalanda and Lakhisarai were resource-poor, landless, or marginal landholders and were found incapable of irrigating their leased-in lands if the lands did not have any existing irrigation source in its vicinity.
- b) **High costs incurred in irrigation were a key deterrent for all kinds of farmers.** Though borewells partly augment the cropping intensity of farmers, those who constructed irrigation infrastructure as well as those who rented them, all farmers who don’t own irrigation infrastructure pay around Rs 150-300 per hour (or Rs 200 per *Kattha*) for renting the pump sets and the borewells.

“Last year, I ended up taking a loan to ensure regular irrigation by renting from another farmer. If I had depended only on rainfall, all my paddy crops would have failed. And with more delays in the arrival of rainfall, we keep incurring higher costs of irrigation.”

–Demo farmers (M) Vaishali

Farmers also find the cost of irrigation using pump sets run by diesel perpetually **increasing with rising diesel prices** thereby reducing the profitability of farming, particularly for small landholders.

- c) **Lack of adequate and regular supply of affordable power limited farmers’ irrigation capacity and pushed them to incur high costs in procuring diesel.** Diesel engines were found to be more expensive to operate, maintain and repair than electricity-run motors, however, the lack of adequate

supply of affordable power remains a constraint in many of these districts, particularly reported by Muzaffarpur, Madhubani, Samastipur and Lakhisarai. “We need regular electricity availability for irrigation. Currently we must spend on diesel. [Demo farmers (M), Samastipur].

- d) Irrigating scattered farmlands is perceived as a difficult and an expensive task.** Scattered Farmlands located at a distance from each other incurred more cost of irrigation. For instance, in Madhubani, farmers renting borewells and pump sets reported spending an **additional amount of money on water pipes**, up to 40-50 kgs of weight, **for sourcing water to irrigate faraway lands**. Demo farmers from Madhubani, Vaishali and Nalanda also reported leaving large portions of lands fallow due to inadequate irrigation infrastructure.

III. LABOUR UNAVAILABILITY

Due to migration, particularly of the male members of the community, labour unavailability becomes a major issue for on-time farm operations. Following are the varied implications of labour unavailability on farmers’ capacity and in ensuring sufficient productivity and returns:

- a) **There is a transition from farm to off-farm work with men seasonally migrating for longer periods to urban areas for work driven by low agricultural returns.** This quote from a Demo farmer (M) of Gaya throws light on the shift in household livelihood patterns, *“Migrants earn up to Rs 80000-90000/year. Why would they stay here and work under scorching heat and still earn less? Most of them plough and irrigate their farms and leave”*.
- b) **Women farmers from migrant households across the sites reported facing more challenges.** Women experience increased responsibilities and work burdens due to labour shortages in the household and community at large caused by male migration. *“Husband sends money to hire labour, but what to do if the labour is not available? We only do it, or sometimes we leave it and don’t do it.”* [Jeevika farmers (F), Lakhisarai]
- c) **Labour scarcity pushes farmers to incur high costs in hiring labour from different villages or blocks, and sometimes even states.** Amongst all the farmers’ groups, Demo farmers who were mostly big farmers were found to be more capable of hiring labour from outside. Non-demo and Jeevika farmers perceived themselves as small farmers and preferred working on the farm by themselves to save labour costs. *“We get very little profit from farming. If we pay Rs 300 per day to labour, we will have no money left.”* [non-Demo farmers (M), Gaya]. In addition to the inability to pay labour costs, women farmers from Jeevika and non-Demo groups expressed having limited knowledge about hiring labour from outside the village: **“We don’t have many contacts outside the village”** [Jeevika farmer (F), Samastipur]

IV: LACK OF ACCESS TO GOOD QUALITY FARM INPUTS

Farmers across the three groups in the seven studied districts shared a range of challenges they faced in terms of access to good quality farm inputs, grouped into six broad categories. The district-wise responses across these six categories of perspectives are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: District-wise response structure of the four major challenges faced in accessing farm inputs.

Districts	Lack of timely availability of seeds, & fertilisers	Quality of seeds	Quality of fertilisers	High costs of farm inputs	Lack of information on good-quality seeds	Lack of Accountability of the input dealers
Muzaffarpur	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Madhubani	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Samastipur	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Vaishali			✓	✓	✓	✓
Gaya	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Nalanda	✓			✓		✓
Lakhisarai			✓	✓		

- a) **Farmers’ satisfaction with the quality of seeds and fertilisers varied based on the type of procurement agency.** Amongst the three farmer groups, non-Demo farmers raised more concerns regarding receiving good quality seeds or fertilisers. Demo farmers reported concerns related to the quality of farm inputs received by public delivery system especially from Muzaffarpur, Madhubani, Vaishali and Gaya districts. As far as the availability of good quality seeds in the market is concerned, all farmer groups across the sites pointed to the gap in demand and supply. Jeevika farmers and some women farmers in non-Demo farmer groups belonging to Jeevika (from Muzaffarpur, Gaya and Nalanda) expressed a level of satisfaction in relation to their access to good quality farm inputs from JEEViKA. Quality of fertilizers was another area of concern raised by the farmers of each group.
- b) **Farmers’ trust in vendors and dealers in the market was determined by networks and relationships among them.** The trust factor was found to be related to the relationship between the farmers and the input dealers and farmers with a “good understanding” with the dealers were confident in receiving good quality inputs. Farmer groups from Muzaffarpur, Madhubani and Vaishali reported having limited choice in buying as the shopkeepers “advise” them to buy or sell them only particular brands of seeds or fertilisers.
- c) The prices of seeds and fertilisers were perceived to be increasing, further exacerbating farmers’ problems. One of the comments from Samastipur non-Demo FGDs points to the complexity of rising prices and the nature of the challenge: *“Fertiliser is available in the market now, but there is no money. Money will come when the paddy harvest is sold, but by then its value in the market will increase.”*

V. LACK OF FINANCIAL CAPITAL AMONG SMALL AND MARGINAL FARMERS

A lack of financial capital was reported as a recurrent challenge among the farmers. They shared the need of **formal, systematic, and institutional credit facilities** from banks or microfinance institutions. Farmers, particularly from non-Demo and Demo categories across the seven districts still face difficulties in accessing institutional credit sources and resort to informal sources where they must pay usurious amounts of interest on loans. Non-Demo farmers are more vulnerable in terms of access to credit. In contrast the credit and loaning patterns of women farmers from Jeevika groups were found to have undergone substantial and positive shifts from private moneylenders to borrowing from their SHG.

“We cannot avail Kisan Credit cards, or any other sources of loans based on our leased land. So, we must incur all the expenses ourselves and share a part of the produce with the landlords. Sometimes we end up mortgaging our household assets.

-Non-Demo Farmers: Lakhisarai

a) Jeevika SHGs—a conducive platform for promoting the access of the rural poor to institutional finance.

Jeevika farmers from all the districts reported having access to regular loans from their SHGs. Participation in SHGs has thereby increased members' access to reliable credit, and reduced women's dependence on men, particularly when there is a cash crunch in the household and men are out-migrating. Some of the other farmer groups such as Demo farmers from Muzaffarpur, Samastipur, Vaishali, Gaya and Nalanda, and non-Demo farmers from Samastipur, Gaya and Nalanda also access Jeevika loans through the SHGs of which they or other women in their household are a part. Jeevika loans were reported to be sought for agricultural purposes as well as for building other livelihood opportunities.

b) Landless, marginal and tenant farmers faces higher level of financial vulnerabilities.

Small landholders and landless farmers, particularly in the non-Demo and women farmers across the seven districts were found leasing in lands for agriculture, which makes them non-eligible to access formal institutional credit. In the absence of formal (on-paper) lease agreements. One of the tenants Jeevika farmers from Samastipur shared, “Even when the crop productivity is not up to the mark, we must pay rent to the landlord. And if there is a delay in the money sent by my [migrant] husband, I take a loan from my SHG. Sometimes if money is not available in my SHG, I take it from relatives and moneylenders. I worry that the landlord will take the land back if I am not able to pay the rent.”

VI. PESTS AND DISEASES

Pest and insect infestation, perceived to be primarily induced by unpredictable rainfall conditions, was reported as another serious constraint to enhanced crop productivity across the respondent groups in the seven districts.

a) Lack of advisory services and support in handling pest and disease occurrences

While occurrences and nature of pests and diseases were common across the districts, some farmer groups were more articulate about the diseases and their unique experiences of dealing with them: Gaya farmers reported crop destruction by Stem Borer and Khaira diseases and their inability to address them amidst a lack of advisory services; Farmers from Lakhisarai experience insects and field rats increasingly

impacting their yields and expressed dissatisfaction in the quality of pesticides to mitigate the crop destruction; and, farmers from Muzaffarpur and Vaishali are waiting for the state's support to stop the regular crop destruction they face by Asian antelopes such as blue buck (referred to as Nilgai or Ghurparas locally) that have been destroying farmers' ready-to-harvest crops for the past few years. Women (Jeevika) farmers from Vaishali articulated the double burden faced by them in managing crop spoilage due to wild animals. One of them commented, "It is difficult for us to continuously remain vigilant against attack by wild animals while also managing household and other care responsibilities."

"There are no fixed market rates of the crop, due to which middlemen tend to gain more than the producers. They have more say and sometimes they raise prices based on a whim".

- Demo farmers, Vaishali

"Women don't go to the markets a lot to sell crops except when their husbands are out-migrating. When buyers come to the village to buy our produce, it is difficult to negotiate with them in the absence of men."

- Jeevika farmers, Muzaffarpur

b) Farmers also reported facing excessive weed growth in their crop fields with rising temperatures and less rain, severely impacting their yields. Though the occurrence of weeds was reported across the district, only some farmers (Demo farmers from Muzaffarpur and Lakhisarai, and Jeevika farmers from Vaishali) were found to be aware of the causes of the same—temperature and texture of the soil (whether it is dry or moist).

c) Lack of information received on fertiliser and pesticide

Farmers were largely unaware of the quantity and timing of fertiliser and pesticide/fungicide application. **The Jeevika farmers were relatively more satisfied with the quality of information received from the Block Programme Managers or Community Resource Persons (CRPs) who are a part of JEEVIKA.** Some of the Demo farmers registered with the KVKs also reported receiving information from Kisan Salahkars but wanted the quality of the information to improve. Non-Demo farmers shared they did not receive sufficient information on the effective application of fertilisers and pesticides.

VII. LACK OF ACCESS TO SYSTEMATIC MARKET STRUCTURE AND MARKET FACILITIES

The absence of proper and reliable marketing facilities and services acts as a demotivation for farmers to expand and diversify their production. Farmer groups from Muzaffarpur, Madhubani, Samastipur and Nalanda perceived the lack of proper marketing infrastructure and facilities as one of the significant limiting factors. Most of the farmers, particularly men farmers travel to the market, some of which are extremely far away, to sell their produce. Some farmer groups such as non-Demo and Demo farmers from Nalanda, and Demo and Jeevika farmers from Muzaffarpur shared that the government purchases their paddy and wheat crops sometimes, however, delay in receiving the payment for the sales was recognised by them as a demotivating factor.

Furthermore, the **prevalence of low market rates** in the region **and the lack of institutional mechanisms** to support the farmers in selling their crops in bigger and more formal markets emerged as other significant market-related challenges (reported by farmer groups from Vaishali and Samastipur). Demo farmers from Vaishali shared their challenging experience with middlemen and fluctuating crop rates. While the Demo farmers shared a more articulate understanding of the market rates and patterns owing to their frequent interactions with the vendors and external agents, women respondents from almost all farmer groups were largely unaware of the same due to their restricted mobility. Women farmers were

found to be more vulnerable as far as market activities were concerned due to their lack of mobility and limited interaction with the external actors owing to the social and gender dynamics of the regions.

VIII: LACK OF INFORMATION OR KNOWLEDGE RELATED TO NEW TECHNOLOGIES AND EXTENSION SYSTEMS

Agricultural extension and access to innovation were perceived to play a crucial role in enhancing production and improving livelihoods. Varied responses were recorded across the farmer groups and seven districts in terms of access to such services.

Demo farmers were found to have enhanced access to agricultural inputs, machinery, and tools from different organizations which made their farming experience more innovative and effective. Some of the Demo farmers also mentioned receiving training on, and their adoption of the DSR method as a part of the training from CSISA.

Across the sites, **Jeevika farmers shared having an improved access to information related to improved agriculture practices, mechanization, and extension services through their self-help groups.** With the support of loans from SHGs and in some instances, remittances from migrating spouses, women reported renting machines from Jeevika to reduce their drudgery on farms. Jeevika farmers exhibited awareness across a range of innovative farming practices such as kitchen gardens, preparing organic manure, and information on farm tools such as tractors, weeders, pesticide spray machines, threshers, seed drills and zero tillage machines.

“If after planting the seeds, the rainfall is inadequate, our seeds burn and very few seeds germinate. We can’t transplant such a small quantity, so we plant the seeds again. This is an extra expense, not only in buying seeds but also in employing labour. Many poor farmers don’t transplant as they can’t incur the additional expense which has no certainty of returns.

-Non-Demo farmers (M), Samastipur

In contrast, non-Demo farmers were found to lack access to extension services or new technologies thereby facing major constraints for innovation and value addition. “The people of Jeevika provide tractors, threshers and spray machines that we can borrow, and they also teach us about new methods of farming.”

3.2.2 Constraints and Challenges specific to nursery establishment

To design interventions to improve farmers’ planting patterns and behaviour, it is important to understand the specific challenges faced by farmers during the sowing of seeds and the overall nursery establishment stage. The previous section captures all the broad and major constraints encountered by farmers in the cropping systems, especially in the last 5 years. This section funnels those perspectives to provide an overview of the challenges specific to nursery establishment that need to be addressed to mitigate risks of yield loss and enhance crop productivity. Figure 3 presents a word cloud illustrating the frequency of the multiple perspectives on key challenges that emerged from across the farmer groups. The size of the phrase/constraining factor portrays the number of FGD responses across farmer groups.

“We face issues related to irregular and delayed rainfall during the nursery establishment which also result into delayed transplanting.

-Farmers (Demo, Non Demo, Jeevika)

Though **low and erratic rainfall** and **delays in the onset of rains during nursery establishment** were considered a perpetual deterrent, the **lack of irrigation infrastructure** and **limited access** to the same emerged as **serious impediments in expanding farmers' agricultural capacity and livelihoods**. Shah et al. (2018) also suggests improving unreliable and expensive irrigation infrastructure as a prerequisite to agricultural growth and resilience in the Eastern Gangetic plains. According to farmers' perspectives across the seven districts, the lack of irrigation infrastructure was further exacerbated by the **high costs involved in agriculture** including costs of diesel for running the pumps, pipes, pump sets, and power cuts leading to increased use and cost of renting the pump sets, elaborated in the earlier sections. Farmer groups from Gaya and Nalanda also articulated the **depletion in groundwater levels** in their areas that force farmers to incur more costs in drawing water from borewells and tubewells during nursery establishment.

Additionally, **unpredictable, and insufficient rains** and **high temperatures burn or dry up the seedlings and prevent the seeds from germinating**. This forces the farmers to **replant their nurseries** in turn increasing their costs and risks, as reported by several farmer groups across the districts.

The **unavailability of labour**, also described in Section 3.2.1 earlier, **further aggravates the challenges associated with the lack of infrastructure and limited financial capital during the nursery establishment period, particularly for women from migrant households**. The lack of access to timely availability of farm inputs (good quality and affordable seeds and fertilisers), labour, and technology (tractors and other agricultural machinery) were other frequently reported challenges, the various aspects of each are described in the earlier sections.

Figure 2: Word cloud illustrating the multiple responses of farmers on the challenges specific to nursery establishment.

3.2.3 Rainfall situation in 2022 and Challenges

Through the lens of agriculture, the rainfall situation in 2022 was characterised by both a drought-like situation, and a situation of waterlogging/overflowing. Farmers across the districts reported the rainfall in 2022 as “less” and “insufficient” compared to the previous year. The insufficiency range that emerged from the farmers’ responses was 75-95% less rainfall than in 2021.

Rainfall was distributed unevenly leading to a drought-like situation during dry spells during the monsoon season and a waterlogging or flood-like situation during continued periods of excessive rainfall. Light rains occurred during the sowing of seeds/establishing nursery in May and early June and no rainfall during transplantation time (Late June-early July). Rainfall occurred erratically in short periods in August. Some farmers highlighted the reduced rainfall during this time in terms of “*so less that even ponds and deep lands were not filled with water*”. Hence, farmers perceived the beginning of the kharif (rice) agricultural season (June-July in 2022), as a drought-like situation. Rainfall arrived towards the end of October, between Durga Puja and Deepawali when some rice varieties were ready to be harvested. During this time the rice fields were overflowing with water, and they were unable to harvest paddy. This FGD excerpt highlights the insufficiency of the rains:

“On the 22nd of May or June, it rained for 12 days. Then after a week of no rains, again it rained for 3 to 4 days then it was drought-like for 4-5 days. During the transplanting time this year, it wasn’t raining. We could transplant our crops but had to incur lots of expenses on irrigation.”

–Jeevika farmers (F), Samastipur

- **Lack of preparedness and awareness to mitigate the impacts of the erratic rainfall situation in 2022.**

All farmers across the districts reported a lack of awareness and preparedness for the less rainfall situation in 2022. Fewer land parcels were cultivated in 2022; In Madhubani and Lakhisarai, farmers across three groups reported cultivating only 50-60% of their lands in 2022 as compared to 2021. The drought-like situation also gave rise to **excessive weed growth** in the farms.

The wait for rainfall during and after transplantation, along with expenses incurred for irrigation, added burden on farmers in the form of loans, risk and uncertainty of adequate produce. Owing to heavy rainfall in October, the accumulation of rainwater on the rice fields during the harvesting period delayed the harvesting as well as reduced production as crops were “washed away”. This further added precarity to the wheat cultivation that was delayed. Farmers across the respondent categories in Muzaffarpur, Madhubani, Vaishali, Nalanda, and Gaya districts also cited a lack of information available to them on techniques to cope with drought-like situations or to increase their production amidst drought-like situations. Largely, the rice-wheat cropping system was significantly affected due to erratic rainfall and lack of irrigation infrastructure.

Some districts emerged as more vulnerable and affected by the rainfall situation than others. For instance, all three categories of farmers from Gaya and Vaishali pointed at the drinking water scarcity due to the rainfall situation. “**Forget farming, we had to struggle to arrange drinking water for a few weeks. The water table had gone down**”, commented one of the Jeevika farmers from Gaya.

3.2.4 Anticipated challenges in the wheat cropping in the coming season (Rabi 2022-23)

Wheat production in these districts is constrained by three commonly emerging critical factors:

a) Unpredictable rainfall, and low moisture levels in the soil was the persisting and primary concern in the wheat cropping system. However, in 2022, due to the occurrence of rainfall right before and during rice harvesting, most farmers across the districts were found to anticipate farmlands to have adequate moisture for planting wheat. At the same time, farmers were also anticipating excessive rainfall and waterlogging to have deposited sand on farmlands making it a cumbersome process to plant wheat. Madhubani Jeevika farmers threw light on this situation: **“Many poor farmers are not able to cultivate wheat after excessive rainfall and waterlogging situation as the sands deposited on the farms needs to be removed by a lot of irrigation that then becomes too expensive”.**

“We didn't know the rainfall would be delayed when we bought seeds of Rs 5000 to 10000 and did the seeding. If we had the mechanism to know the rainfall prediction or any prior information related to rainfall, we would not have done it and would have been saved from wasting money.”

- Demo farmers, Nalanda

b) Late rice harvests to cause a delay in planting wheat timely : A key concern was the delay in wheat planting due to the delay in rice planting caused by erratic monsoon and a drought-like situation, thereby leading late harvesting of paddy, The income from the sale of rice crops was found to be one of the primary sources of investment in buying farm inputs and arranging other machines and tools required for wheat cultivation. Hence, several farmers, especially across non-Demo and Jeevika groups perceived themselves to be in a vulnerable situation in terms of arranging finances due to the overall delay.

c) Incidence of diseases and pests and lack of timely availability of good quality seeds, fertilisers, and pesticides to mitigate impacts of diseases was a critical impediment, true to the overall cropping system, but specific to the wheat cropping system. Farmers from across districts described the shortage of good quality and affordable seeds and fertilisers in the market for wheat crops and the high process of farm inputs. Low and erratic rainfall and high temperatures increase the susceptibility of the crops to pests and weeds thereby multiplying the need for pesticides. While many farmers across the three groups received improved quality seeds and fertilisers from Jeevika, Demo farmers with better access to resources reported procuring farm inputs from outside the state (Demo farmers, Madhubani).

3.3 Rice planting and transplanting dates

3.3.1 Timeline-related awareness and practices in rice cultivation

The perception of farmers in their capacity to plant on time varies considerably, shaped by multifaceted enabling factors and constraints. This section presents timeline-related scenarios in rice cultivation in three parts: a) Farmers' knowledge and awareness of planting timing, b) farmer practices, primarily as a response to the rainfall situation, and c) barriers to adopting ideal practices on planting timing. Table 5. Presents an overview of the timeline-related awareness and practices of farmers, and the perceived challenges are explained in the text.

Though across the districts, farmer groups perceived Rohini (May 25 to June 8) and Mrigashira (June 8–June 20) Nakshatras as the ideal time for nursery raising, a large proportion of farmers carried out seeding the nursery in Ardra Nakshatra (June 22-July 5). Some farmers, for instance, in Lakhisarai articulated different sowing times for different varieties of crops. Overall, **the time taken for raising the nursery**

(seedlings) according to the farmers was in the range of 15-25 days, with the most common practice being 20-22 days. There was almost negligible difference in the awareness of seeding-planting timelines across different farmer groups. For instance, in Gaya, the Demo, non-Demo and Jeevika farmers shared that the sowing should start in Rohini (between May 25 to June 8) and Mrigashira (between June 8 to June 20) Nakshatras and transplanting should be carried out towards the end of June month or Ardra (between June 22 to July 5) Nakshatra. Awareness of differing sowing times based on the varieties of rice emerged only from the Demo farmers' FGD.

Farmer groups across the districts reported facing a delay in transplanting in 2022, primarily reported to be caused by the late arrival of rainfall.

Farmers with irrigation facilities prepared the nurseries in Rohini (May 25-June 8) or Mrigashira (June 8-June 20), and the farmers who had limited access to irrigation through renting waited for their chance and prepared nurseries in Mrigashira. The timeline of seeding also depends on the seed variety. For instance, traditional rice was seeded in Rohini Nakshatra (May 25-June 8) while Hybrid rice, which is relatively shorter in duration, was seeded later, in Ardra Nakshatra (June 22-July 5).

Farmers with no access to any irrigation source waited for the rainfall to even prepare the nursery which caused them further delays in the transplanting process. A delay in rainfall caused a drought-like situation and raised the temperature limiting the germination of seeds in the nurseries. Many farmer groups reported reduced yield and wastage of financial capital in farm inputs which was lost due to delays in rainfall in the year 2022.

Table 5: Transplanting date scenarios across districts

	MUZAFFARPUR	MADHUBANJIR	SAMASTIPUR	VAISHALI	GAYA	NALANDA	LAKHISARAI
AWARENESS (What they know)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: Mrigashira ● Ideal time for nursery raising: 18-25 days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: Rohini & Mrigashira ● Ideal time for nursery: 15-20 days ● <u>Ideal time for transplanting:</u> June 15-July 30 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: June ● Ideal time for nursery raising: 20-22 days. ● <u>Ideal time for transplanting:</u> June 15-July 15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: Mrigashira ● Ideal time for nursery: 20-22 days ● <u>Ideal time for transplanting:</u> June end (Ardra) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: Rohini & Mrigashira ● Ideal time for nursery raising: 21-30 days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: late Rohini and early Ardra ● Ideal time for nursery raising: 20-25 days ● <u>Ideal time for transplanting:</u> Ardra 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ideal sowing time: Long duration crop in Rohini, medium duration in early Ardra, short duration in middle of Ardra. ● Ideal time for nursery: 20-22 days
PRACTICE (What they did in 2022)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan backwards from harvesting in Durga puja or Chhath ● Seeds sowed before June 15 ● Transplanting after June 15 ● Delay in transplanting-rainfall 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nursery raising in lowlands: May 15-May 31 ● Nursery raising in uplands: May 25-June 6 ● Delay in transplanting by 20-30 days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Nursery is done when rainfall arrives. ● Seeding started in late June ● Transplanting in late July ● Delay in transplanting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeding done in Mrigshira and Ardra ● Seeding delayed ● Transplanting delayed by 10-15 days due to delay in rains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sowing and planting in Ardra. ● Traditional rice- Rohini. ● Hybrid rice in Ardra ● Transplanting Delayed by 25-50 days 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeding done in Rohini and Adra ● Transplanting delayed by 20-30 days ● 40-45 days for germination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Seeding on time ● Transplanting Delayed. ● June last week ● 30-45 days for seed germination

Other factors preventing timely transplanting were: labour unavailability, further amplified by delays in rainfall (and hence delays in transplanting) pushing the labourers to out-migrate to other cities for their livelihoods, in turn, raising the cost of labour that had to be then hired from outside the village or seek the short supply of remaining local labour; and, the timely availability of, and rising costs of fertilisers and seeds.

Women and poor farmers were found to be more vulnerable to the constraints of planting delay:

Across the farmer groups and sites, farmers recognised that men and women face similar challenges as they farm together and are a part of the same households. However, on further probing, it was acknowledged across the sites that women faced more problems than men. This narrative emerged primarily from Jeevika farmer groups and from Demo farmers (mostly men) FGD of Vaishali, Madhubani, Lakhisarai and Nalanda. While Demo farmers centred the reasons on women’s inability to do heavy physical work on the farm, a lack of exposure to operating heavy machines and modern technology, and interacting with vendors and buyers in the market, Jeevika farmers perceived the absence of their migrant husbands as a key factor increasing their work burden making it difficult for them to manage all by themselves on time.

“Women face more problems than men as they cannot do heavy work, cannot operate heavy machines, or plough and they are dependent on men. This dependency can cause delays. Easy for men to arrange, carry and organise pipes & machines.”

–Demo farmers, Lakhisarai

“Women whose husbands migrate face more challenges. She must do all the household and outside work by herself, and the burden of work can cause delays in purchasing inputs and planting.”

–Jeevika farmers, Samastipur

Non-Demo and Jeevika farmers also pointed to the socio-economic context of farmers which limits or enables farmers to plant on time. For instance, challenges differ whether the farmer is landless or a big farmer. It was perceived that while rich or resourceful farmers are less likely to get delayed in timely planting as they can arrange labor from outside the state (from Punjab) and organize other farm-related logistics and complete tasks faster, resource-poor farmers must wait for their chance to avail services thereby enduring delays.

3.3.2 Common methods of planting

The common methods of rice planting across the seven districts are a) **broadcasting the seeds**, and b) **preparing the rice nursery and transplanting the seedlings**, following a sequence of ploughing the field–irrigating (farmers with irrigation source)–sowing the seeds to form a nursery–uprooting the seedlings ideally after 20-22 days to plant into the rice fields. Many farmer groups also reported doing seed treatment by soaking the seeds overnight and drying them before sowing them to make a nursery. After the seeds germinate, the seedlings are uprooted and planted in straight lines on their farm by the farmers. However, some farmer groups such as Demo farmers of Lakhisarai, non-Demo farmers of Muzaffarpur, Vaishali and Nalanda, and Jeevika farmers of Muzaffarpur and Lakhisarai also reported ploughing the land and broadcasting the seeds without preparing a nursery.

Demo farmers and some of the non-Demo and Jeevika farmers indicated using the Direct Seeded Rice (DSR) method to plant their rice seeds using zero tillage machine, driven by the CSISA project in 2022.

3.3.3 Decision-making on Transplanting Dates

The key determinants for the decision making on transplanting dates by farmers related to Puddled transplanted rice and direct seeded rice were influence by various factors - climate and onset of monsoon, irrigation facilities, socio-economic status, labour availability, access to input and resources and in few cases, it was also found to be influenced by weather forecast.

- **Multiple climate-related factors determined farmers' capacity and decisions in timely sowing and transplantation.**

The onset of monsoon, access to reliable irrigation facilities, distance between the irrigation source and the farmland, access to agricultural machinery and tools such as tractors for ploughing and land preparation, availability of seeds and fertilisers, and labour, and capital to pay for crucial operations were some of the key factors. Though the challenges reported were common across the farmer groups in seven districts, they impacted the farmers in varying intensities based on the intersectional factors shaping their vulnerability contexts. At the household level, farmers reported making decisions on planting timings based on the Nakshatras, availability of financial capital, access to agricultural infrastructure and variety of paddy seeds, and sometimes based on weather forecast checked on the internet or received agro advisories on the mobile and in consultation with village elders.

Figure 3: Factors determining transplanting dates by farmers across the three groups.

- **Socio-economic status and access to inputs and resources impacted farmers' planting time scenario.**

Farmers were found to differ in their landholding size and access levels to agricultural inputs, mechanisation and investment capacity thereby determining their ability to prepare nurseries or transplant on time.

For example, Jeevika farmers in Madhubani pointed out that though they receive tractors and other agricultural tools through their SHGs, it is shared between 10-12 women, so others must wait. "Another woman from the same FGD shared an interesting perspective on differential access to the tractor, *"In my SHG, one of the didi's lands is in the middle—one where the tractor cannot go. And the farm adjacent to that belongs to another farmer who had ploughed earlier so he didn't let the tractor pass through his fields. As a result, she could not do direct seeded rice."* Likewise, though the migration-induced shortage of labour was reported as an important determinant in transplanting on time from all farmer groups, farmers with cash availability hire labourers, sometimes at a higher cost and get their nursery and transplanting done on time.

"Farmers owning borewells and pump sets can manage sowing nurseries and carry out almost timely transplantation of seedlings".

Non -Demo Farmers – Nalanda

Similarly, at the village level, Irrigation water is generally made accessible by pump owners to other farmers who rent the pump sets on a pay-per-hour basis so that variability in prices and availability further constrain timely planting. Another factor influencing planting time at the village level, particularly reported by Vaishali and Gaya farmers was the susceptibility of early planters to blue bucks or pest and disease pressures due to crops on a small number of plots rather than being diluted across the landscape.

Farming-related decision-making in the household was governed by the local gender dynamics.

Intra-household decision-making was reported as being done by both men and women together across the farmer groups and districts, except in a few instances. For instance, in Gaya and Vaishali, Demo and non-Demo farmers held men responsible for making these decisions, being the head of the household. Mobility of women in these areas appeared to be restricted and their participation in the farm was also limited to tasks assigned to them by the men of the household. Jeevika farmers in these areas, however, shared that planting-related decisions were taken by both men and women or by women when men were out-migrating. Moreover, Jeevika farmers in all the districts described the decision-making process as consultative as women perceive that SHGs act as a significant platform for providing information and services in enhancing their agricultural-related knowledge and capacity, yield and men were also found recognizing that in these areas.

“Men cannot farm without the support of women. We both make decisions together, but he goes out more, so he knows more. So, I trust his decision. Sometimes I also share the information I receive from my SHGs- on seed treatment or farming techniques, and then he also listens.”

-Jeevika women farmers, Samastipur

3.4 Coping mechanism to manage drought and flood-like situations in agriculture.

Research suggests that improving unreliable and expensive irrigation infrastructure is a prerequisite for mitigating climate-related risks and developing the capacity and resilience of farmers in the EGP (Shah et al., 2018). This section presents the measures adopted by farmers to address the challenges and constraints primarily caused due to unpredictable rainfall causing drought-like or excessive waterlogging (flood-like) situations.

3.4.1 Solutions adopted to address rainfall-timing-related challenges.

- **To overcome the impact of drought-like situations in agriculture, borewells were constructed by individual farmers and rented by other farmers.** In the context of an overall absence of government-supported or government-provided borewells, farmers with more resources were found to construct borewells at an individual level. Diesel or electricity-run pump sets were also procured by them that were used to extract groundwater out of the borewells. The resource-poor farmers were found to rent the irrigation structure from owners of irrigation facilities, and they reported facing delays often in accessing the borewells as the owners rented out the pump set after completing irrigating their own fields.
- **To address the low germination of seeds induced by high temperatures, farmers adopt measures such as re-establishment of nurseries/re-seeding.** In case of destruction of the nursery, farmers with resources establish nurseries again and then plant the saplings when they germinate. Farmers with

fewer resources transplant remaining seedlings or don't transplant fearing another round of disappointment. Responses across the farmer groups differ, for instance, replanting is practised by only non-Demo farmers from Nalanda and Samastipur, Demo farmers from Madhubani and Vaishali, and all three farmer groups from Gaya and Lakhisarai. Another mechanism adopted by the farmers to cope with low yield during drought (and excessive waterlogging during harvest) was planting late-flowering varieties of rice. Some farmers preferred planting a combination of early flowering and late flowering varieties to incur fewer losses in the context of unpredictable rainfall.

- **Innovation support from institutions such as JEEViKA and CSISA initiative was perceived as reliable and adopted by farmers to cope with climate variabilities:** Another theme on coping mechanism that emerged from the perspective of Demo farmers, but also from non-Demo and Jeevika farmers was that of adopting the CSISA project activities. Demo farmers reported using zero tillage machines for planting wheat in Rabi following the practice of Zero tillage in wheat and doing direct-seeded rice (DSR) in Kharif. Farmers found DSR as a cost saving technology, no yield penalty with less labour input. They shared the success in DSR is dependent on good rainfall and proper weed management. Demo farmers from Gaya and Muzaffarpur expressed using CSISA recommended seeds or short-duration variety. As discussed in earlier sections, JEEViKA acted as a platform of support by providing tools and resources to cope with climate-induced risks particularly to women farmers and hence their household. Jeevika and many non-Demo and Demo farmers were found to be receiving good quality paddy and wheat seeds and fertilisers from JEEVIKA to support their crop cycle, especially planting on time. Jeevika farmers from Gaya and Samastipur reported arranging fertilisers for wheat and rice through JEEViKA before it became scarce.
- **Collective efforts were recognised to offer great potential for community innovation and agricultural development but were also considered impractical due to an overall lack of trust among farmers.**

Collective efforts were adopted in some districts especially by Jeevika farmers to cope with the challenges of drought, such as constructing nurseries together in a place with access to irrigation, farmers with motors helping other farmers, and supporting each other as agricultural labour during transplanting and harvesting. A collective approach adopted to address the lack of irrigation facilities emerged from non-Demo groups in Lakhisarai and Nalanda, and Jeevika farmers from Madhubani. 10-12 farmers collectively constructed a borewell in one instance, in another, Jeevika farmers co-procured a pump-set and placed it in an area accessible to all the SHG members. The ownership, sharing, renting and usage patterns of borewells differ across the districts and farmer groups based on the social norms of the village. Such innovations here and there gives a hope for collective efforts to be an innovative solution to deal with irrigation issues at the field level but is totally dependent on the management process involved inculcating trust and transparency related to management. An overall lack of trust was cited as a factor behind the scattered and sporadic instances of collective efforts. "Nothing can be done collectively. People think why I should give my money to others. It is an individual issue, so we must tackle it accordingly. The trust is lacking. [Demo farmers, Muzaffarpur]. This comment from Jeevika farmers in Vaishali also pointed to the lack of labour and other resources further disabling any opportunity for collective efforts "If a didi will help me in my farms after her farm work is completed, I will have to wait for her work to finish first and hence will get late. Everyone wants to finish theirs first. In this case who will help whom first remain a question?"

However, from the overall perspectives and practices being followed by Jeevika farmers, **"a strong possible potential of SHGs emerged that have the potential to trigger the pathway for collective**

effort through strategically strengthening their social capital, and management skills and creating an enabling ecosystem, to adopt community innovation aimed at mitigating climate-related challenges.

3.4.2 Support required to implement solutions for nursery establishment and transplanting.

The support anticipated and articulated by the farmer groups across the districts were on the lines of the major constraints being faced by farmers in their cropping system. A predominant support anticipated from the farmers was the government support in ensuring a reliable source of irrigation. Along with constituting borewells and tubewells other sources such as rivers, canals, and ponds can also be efficiently used. On the construction of groundwater irrigation, an interesting perspective emerged from the non-Demo farmers from Gaya and Nalanda: *“We should have other sources of irrigation also other than borewells or tubewells because so many borewells will overexploit the groundwater. The water table is already declining- now if we need to dig a borewell, we must dig it much deeper as compared to earlier time* [non-Demo farmers, Nalanda]. Demo and non-Demo farmers from Lakhisarai also shared the need for connecting canals with the river Ganga as a prospective solution to deal with irrigation-related challenges. Another aspect of enabling smooth irrigation was a **regular supply of electricity at affordable rates so that farmers could use pump sets for irrigation.** Table 6 lists the recurring and frequently answered perspectives on support expected from external agencies, particularly from the government. It also lists some of the unique perspectives that emerged from FGDs with specific farmer groups or from specific district.

In the context of a shortage of labour, farmers perceive agricultural machines and equipment as important tools to reduce their burden and drudgery along with saving time.

This was especially raised by women farmers in Jeevika who find tractors, drum seeders, pesticide spraying machines or other machines received from their SHGs as critical to support them when the male member of the family migrates. However, some of the Jeevika farmers, and some other Demo and non-Demo farmers receiving services from Jeevika expected the Jeevika support to become more regular and cater to more people. This excerpt from the Jeevika FGD in Samastipur highlights their expectation: **“There is one tractor in the VO, so it is not available on time to everyone as everyone starts farming together. We keep waiting for our turn so sometimes it gets delayed. If there can be a greater number of tractors, then it would benefit more people?”** [Jeevika farmers, Samastipur]

Farmers expected regular and easy access to innovation, extension services, and credit facilities to improve their effectiveness and efficiency of agriculture. Other key areas of support to facilitate a smoother nursery establishment and transplanting recounted by farmers are -timely availability of good quality high yielding seeds and address fertiliser shortage and check on rising prices; Systematic and uncomplicated process of availing loans and institutional sources of credit to address the lack of financial capital; regular training and information on improved varieties of seeds and innovative methods of farming to increase crop yields were other arena farmers shared.

Amongst the three groups of farmers, the nature of support expected by farmers was largely the same, with slight variations in the context of their subjective geographical needs and groups affiliation. However, apart from receiving financial and infrastructural support from their SHG systems, Jeevika farmers shared receive training on innovative methods of farming that they would like to expand to include more livelihood enhancement activities. Demo farmers also reported receiving good quality seeds, zero tillage machines and innovative cropping techniques from the CSISA project and while some farmers

recognised their cost saving, labour saving agriculture practices with no yield, a few farmers expected the project activities run by different stakeholders to become more robust.

Table 6: Overview of the support required to implement solutions for transplanting.

	Recurring perspectives	Unique perspectives
Support anticipated by the farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Borewells and Tubewells → An alternate and reliable source of irrigation (rivers, canals & ponds) → Timely availability of seeds & fertiliser (one week before planting) → Agricultural inputs at affordable rates → Agricultural machines and tools (tractor, spraying, zero tillage, harvesting, pump sets) → Information on using machines. → High-yielding seed varieties → Financial support → Regular supply of electricity for irrigation → Information on agricultural techniques to improve farming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Specific irrigation alternatives: Canal on Gandak River [Vaishali]; Water from Kunder Dam [Lakhisarai] → Farmer Producer Organisation (FPO) as a platform for providing support in extension and marketing. [Samastipur Demo] → Information on planting timings [Samastipur non-Demo] → Support from other farmers (mobilisation for creating a facilitative environment who cut canal supply) [Madhubani Jeevika] → Reliable & regular support from the government for various services (inputs, crop marketing, blue buck mitigation.) [Muzaffarpur all groups]

3.5 Agro-advisory systems

Agricultural advisory systems are important to not only enhance agricultural productivity and income but also to strengthening ties between farmers, research, agricultural education, and other private and civil society actors (Faure et al., 2012). In the context of extreme climate variabilities faced by farmers in India, **reliable and economical agro-advisory services are crucial for the dissemination of timely information to mitigate risks and losses in agricultural productivity and income.** For example, timely information on monsoons would help farmers make decisions to sow at the right time to cope with rainfall-related uncertainties particularly in the rain-fed areas (Raghuvanshi et al. 2018).

This section presents the opportunities and challenges of the current agro-advisory systems shared by the farmers in the seven districts and their feedback and expectations for strengthening the agro advisory system.

Sections 3.2 and 3.3 put forward farmers perspective on climate-induced uncertainties and associated risks as the most critical constraint faced by farmers in the various stages of agriculture. It also emerged during the discussions, that at the farmer level, their self-perception of distress and vulnerability to the climate variabilities was primarily induced by a lack of preparedness for the unpredictable weather. A general lack of awareness and access to information/advisories about accurate weather predictions and rainfall timings emerged as the challenges being faced by the farmers.

3.5.1. Sources of information and barriers to information

Farmers receive advisories from different sources and stakeholders ranging from village elders and their traditional knowledge systems to government and several non-governmental and private entities. The sources of information were similar as well as varied across the districts and farmer groups. Figure 4 provides an overview of the sources of advisories across 21 FGDs with three farmer groups- Demo, Non-Demo and Jeevika. Across the farmer groups, **village elders and their intergenerational and traditional knowledge of farmers in the villages remain a significant source of information on farming practices**. Additionally, Kisan Salahkars (Agriculture department extension personal), were also perceived to be one of the important sources of information related to agriculture (Figure 4).

As described in the earlier sections, **Demo farmer groups had increased access to innovation and information from the government and different private organizations, and non-governmental organizations**. The primary sources of information for the Demo farmers were text or WhatsApp messages from KVKs and the agriculture university (PUSA), and correspondence with Kisan Salahkars in the district of Samastipur, Demo farmers were found receiving information and support from different agencies operational in their vicinity like the Dr. Reddy Foundation, and Demo farmers from Nalanda received pesticide spraying machines and information on effective pesticide utilisation from Oxfam and HDFC Foundation. Information from the CSISA project was also found to be a regular source of information by several demo farmer groups in recent times.

Non-Demo farmer groups relied heavily on the experience of village elders and information from Kisan Salahkar. They perceived themselves to be receiving “no reliable information for improving agriculture.” This comment from the non-Demo farmer group (M) FGD in Lakhisarai exemplifies that:

For receiving information from KVK, PUSA or the Meteorological department, your number should be registered with them. And we don't know the right people who can help us in registering our numbers.” Though both Demo and non-Demo farmer groups reported receiving financial and mechanisation support from Jeevika (documented in earlier sections), most of them shared the need for also receiving advisories through JEEViKA.

Figure 4: Number of FGDs that reported the key sources of information across the three farmer groups in 7 districts (n=21 FGDs).

For Jeevika farmers, the intermediaries between the SHGs at the village level and JEEViKA at the block level were their primary sources of information. These intermediaries (block resource persons (BRPs) and Village resource persons (VRPs)) provided them with information on improved farming techniques, and advisory on quantity, quality and timing of plantation. Krishi Salahkars were also reported by Jeevika farmers as another source of information. Women farmers making market visits to buy farm

inputs also considered shopkeepers as an accessible source of information on the quality and application of seeds.

Gender, level of education, economic situation, mobility, age, position in the household and access to the different tools and platforms to receive information determined farmers’ actual chances of accessing advisory services. Figure 5 illustrates an overall understanding of the **barriers to accessing advisory services**, faced by farmers across the seven districts. Presenting a hierarchical view (descending starting from the left) of FGD responses, seven rectangular and different colour boxes depict seven barriers and the data's value determines each box's size.

- **Low levels of literacy** were found to be a key constraint among farmers to read and interpret advisories received either as messages on mobile phones or accessing smartphone applications, posters and other print materials.
- The **gender issue** is particularly critical in developing countries and is addressed by numerous authors who demonstrate the **difficulties encountered by women in obtaining advisory services** (e.g. Lahai et al., 1999, in Nigeria; Saima et al., 2005, in Pakistan, and Kansime et al., 2019, in India).

Figure 5: Barriers to accessing advisory services across three farmer groups. (n=21 FGDs)

Multiple perspectives on **women’s low access to advisory services emerged from our study sites, especially in terms of owing and accessing ICT tools such as mobile phones, television or radio.** Most women across Jeevika groups and non-Demo groups reported not having a personal mobile phone making them dependent on their children to provide them with the information. **“Mobile phones are mostly with the children so when any message comes–about rainfall dates or something. They inform us.”** [Jeevika (F) farmers, Gaya]. Many women can’t read, making them dependent on other household members, especially children to read them the advisory messages that are received as messages on mobile phones. Jeevika farmers from Vaishali also pointed to the timing of programmes on the television which they end up missing because they are working on the farms.

- **Low access to smartphones and their usage, especially for small and marginal farmers and women acted as another barrier to access advisories.** On one hand, a few Demo and non-Demo farmers were found using internet and mobile applications (on weather and agriculture-related advisories) on their smartphones, on the other, all women farmers (Jeevika and non-Demo) and many men farmers reported not owning a smartphone. However, some men farmers were aware of the usefulness of smartphones and the different sources of information that can be acquired. Farmers owning smartphones also commented on challenges with the user interface with their smartphones or in other words their **digital illiteracy**. Some other farmers mentioned that they don’t buy it due to a

lack of finances and lack of digital know-how. **“What will we do with a smartphone? We don’t know how to use it and we will need so much money to recharge it.** [non-Demo farmers, Nalanda]

- **Low access to television and radio acted as barriers as local news was considered** (especially by male farmers) **a useful source of information on farming methods and weather conditions to decide planting dates and techniques.** Some Demo and non-Demo farmers were found following television programmes like Krishi Darshan to obtain timing-related information. Women farmers (Jeevika) found taking out time to watch television programmes was a difficult task as they were overburdened with housework and farm work.
- Figure 4 illustrates **Kisan Salahkars** as an important source of information for farmers across the categories and districts. Farmers further shared the need to strengthen this mechanism with regular visit of Kisan Salahkar on their field.

3.5.2 Ways of improving current advisory systems

I. THEMATIC AREAS ANTICIPATED

To design contextual, effective, and signalled agro-advisory systems, it is important to listen to, and consider, the perspectives, concerns and expectations of farmers using the advisories. Farmers’ responses on improving the current agro-advisory systems have been categorised into the following themes or areas of information. **These suggestions and expectations can act as feedback to the programmes seeking to improve the local agro-advisory system in each context.** The comment from one of the FGDs typifies the relevance of context-specific agro-advisories:

“The advisory that we receive should be contextual and non-generic. The situation of the neighbouring panchayat can be different to ours. So, information should be tailor-made for us so that we can make effective use of it and improve our agriculture capacity and returns.”

–Demo farmers, Vaishali

- **Accurate and timely information on rainfall.** Every farmer group across the sites expected to receive more accurate and timely information on weather conditions, especially rainfall to minimise losses. Moreover, farmers from some Demo groups perceived that the rainfall information should not only be about the percentage of rainfall anticipated but also information on the amount of rainfall.
- **Reliable information on sowing and transplanting time:** The lack of accurate information on rainfall followed by the limited and unreliable information on planting time is another key challenge faced by farmers. Jeevika farmers (F) from Gaya remarked on the importance of timely rice planting to avoid costly groundwater irrigation, **“Seed germination and crop productivity depends so much on when the planting was done. Our biggest worry is what if we plant and it will not rain. And then we will end up incurring huge expenses on irrigation.”** This comment from non-Demo farmers (M) from Madhubani exemplifies that though farmers recognise the importance of timely planting, they find themselves at the receiving end of limited information that aggravates their other vulnerabilities: **“We will be able to save our crop loss and high expenses of irrigation, replanting or pesticides if know the right time of planting.”**
- **Information on, and access to, genuine quality seeds, fertilisers and pesticides, and effective application techniques.** Though Demo, Jeevika and non-Demo farmers reported receiving farm inputs from different organisations, they were largely dissatisfied with the limited information on the effective use of seeds and fertilisers. Only Jeevika farmers reported a certain level of satisfaction with

the advisories received through BRPs, but they expected more practices regularly. Overall, the farmers expected advisories on the quality of seeds to improve production, real prices of seeds and fertilisers, good quality fertilisers and pesticides and their effective application to prevent crops from insects, and strategies to manage weeds. **“We want advisory on different varieties of seeds based on seasons, on pesticides -how to apply and how much to apply”** [Demo farmers (M), Gaya]

II. PREFERRED ADVISORY PLATFORMS

In the context of farmer’s perception of barriers to accessing information and advisory services, presented in Section 3.5.1, this section provides an overview of ways articulated by farmers to improve the medium of disseminating agro-advisory systems. Figure 6 presents farmer group-wise pie charts and the mediums they perceive as convenient and effective.

Face-to-face meetings in the village or Aam Sabhas and “Kisan Chaupals” emerged as the most preferred medium of receiving advisories. For Jeevika farmers, **SHG meetings** were the most convenient platform that the resource persons could use as platforms to disseminate knowledge and information on varied topics and mitigate the information asymmetry especially faced by rural women. The use of **information and communication technologies (ICTs)**, such as mobile phones, smartphones, televisions, radio, and internet services **was found to be another effective mode of dissemination of technologies, practices, and other services to farmers.** Due to low levels of literacy², audio messages on mobile phones or audio calls were reported to be more convenient. Nevertheless, farmers were also comfortable with text messages on mobile phones. In some cases of smartphone users, voice messages, audio, and videos on WhatsApp, and were also suggested as a potential platform to be explored.

Other preferred platforms were through other creative and in-person modes such as micing or announcements through autos and printed posters. Demo and non-Demo farmers also consider **Kisan Salahkar** as a useful intermediary for knowledge dissemination and exchange. Jeevika farmers (in earlier sections) reported irregular and inequitable access to Kisan Salahkars, hence, they considered SHGs as the more reliable and accountable platform. The pie chart also illustrates the Demo farmers’ greater access to agro-advisory modes as compared to Jeevika or non-Demo farmers.

² In Bihar, Literacy rate of women in rural areas: 55%; literacy rate of men in rural areas: 77% (NFHS-5, 2019-20)

Figure 6: Preferred and accessible platforms and methods for receiving information.

III. LANGUAGE AND TIMING OF ADVISORY INTERFACE

Farmers' language preferences for receiving advisory services are determined by the socio-demographic context of the area. Largely due to low levels of literacy, it emerged that farmers expected messages and information in easily understandable language. Farmers expressed a certain level of comfort with receiving advisories in Hindi, however, **local languages** were recognised as a definite added advantage. **“It will be easy for people like us who don't know much clean Hindi and have also not studied much.”** [Jeevika farmers, Nalanda] **“The information is fine in Hindi as we all know Hindi, but it should be clear message on how to apply that or how a certain technology is adaptable in our field. Otherwise, how will we make use of any information** [Demo farmers, Madhubani]

As far as the **timing of the information is concerned, farmers' preferences varied based on the nature of their livelihood and household activities in which they were engaged.** Farmers were of the understanding that advisories should start **2-3 weeks before planting season and should continue throughout the crop cycle.** Messages should be disseminated at different times of the day. This is important to cater to individuals engaged in different livelihood activities, especially for **women who are engaged in agriculture as well as in the household.** While some farmers preferred receiving advisories in the afternoon/evening or the early mornings before leaving for the field, others preferred during the daytime or after lunch when there is a short resting time.

CHAPTER 4: CONCLUSION

Unpredictable and unevenly distributed rainfall patterns were a major determinant for farmers' decision on the planting of crops. The analysis in this report pursued to understand the farmer's perspective regarding the major constraints in the rice-wheat cropping systems. The constraints shared by farmers were further delved deeper and analysed to understand the interaction between the multiple layers of vulnerabilities faced and shared by the farmers and the potential opportunities and mechanisms for coping and building adaptation and resilience to the constraints. In the studied sites in Bihar, the climate situation is perceived to be playing a critical role in deciding what crops are to be grown, how (farming practices), and when (timing of planting), thereby determining crop yields amidst the small-holder farming systems. Extreme weather patterns have adverse impacts on the stability of yields of rainfed crops like rice and wheat, the two primary crops in the region. Lack of irrigation infrastructure and the absence of assured access to timely irrigation, impacts farmers in varying intensity. Crop yields were also found to be affected by the quality of seeds and fertilisers. Farmers also shared the challenge with the timely availability of good quality farm inputs making them susceptible to greater risk of yield loss. The lack of financial capital by small and marginal farmers to access farm inputs were further affected by the climate uncertainties and risk associated with the unpredictable monsoon. The labour unavailability due to increased migration of men and shift in livelihood patterns to non-farm migrant work also act as a bottleneck in timely sowing and transplanting activities. Lack of proper marketing facilities, and lack of timely and assured advisory emerged as the other systemic challenges exacerbating the vulnerability of rice-wheat cropping systems.

The report also presents an analysis of the findings through a gender lens to describe the contextualised and varied experiences of the farmers thereby recognising the importance of diversity and heterogeneity in designing programmes and policies to address cropping system challenges. Out of the three groups of farmers in the study, Demo farmers were relatively big farmers with larger land parcels and more improved access to inputs, information, and other services, as compared to the resource-poor farmers in non-Demo and Jeevika groups. The findings demonstrate that the challenges and opportunities of the poor and marginalised farmers depends on their resource-base, restrictive gender norms of the communities and the structural disadvantage for instance, landless or tenant farmers have no access to irrigation infrastructure and often cannot avail government subsidies and schemes related to agriculture. Access to scarcely available labour was gendered and skewed towards the big farmers as women and poor farmers lacked the finances and networks to hire labour, that were often procured from outside the village. Moreover, women from poorer households worked as labourers on their own and other farms while bigger farmers "considered it ideal if women looked after the household and left the outward-facing work on men." While out-migrating men added to women's work burden, it also opened spaces for women to participate in outward-facing stages of the agricultural value chains like marketing and innovation, especially through SHGs. Access to mechanisation, innovation, extension services and information was inequitable, wherein bigger farmers in Demo groups could contact agriculture intermediaries and other external organisations easily for information and services while other groups were largely not a part of such networks. This trend was, however, positively changing with women's increased access to, and adoption of, services and mechanisation through JEEViKA-SHGs.

JEEViKA-SHGs emerged as a promising platform for augmenting agriculture and improving the experiences of smallholder farmer households, especially women. In addition to providing financial benefits in the form of loans to invest in agriculture, SHGs also offered information, innovation, mechanisation, and extension services to its members. This has strong potential and can be explored to

act as a vehicle of change for the reliable scientific recommendations and advisories reaching out to the farmers in the state. Women farmers now have reliable access to larger pools of capital and other services providing them with a safety net and decreasing their dependence on male members of the family. Men farmers also recognised the potential of SHGs in addressing some of the structural barriers in agriculture faced especially by poor and marginalised farmers. Though this report does not explore the strength of social capital in the SHGs in securing benefits for agricultural improvement, several studies have presented evidence for the same. Hence, limited instances of collective action in these regions in the form of synchronous rice planting, rice-wheat cropping system, use of irrigation sources or any other community innovation to mitigate structural or climate-related challenges could be tapped by leveraging the institutional platforms of JEEViKA SHGs. In summary, for programs to have diversified reach and benefits, SHGs can be utilized as a platform for transmitting information, disseminating improved farming practices as well and generating demands and feedback to improve the contextual significance of the intervention. As an innovative impact-oriented platform SHGs are playing productive roles in mainstreaming and empowering women in agriculture. (Munshi.et .al 2021)

Addressing the various constraints facing farmers in the rice-wheat cropping system and enhancing agroecosystem resilience is a special challenge that requires efficient channelising of resources to not only strengthen farmers' adaptive capacity to climate variabilities but also address their structural disadvantages. The vulnerabilities of individual farmers and households can vary in response to different constraints. Equally, their ability to cope with major barriers can also change over time. Time management in the rice-wheat cropping system is crucial catering to the challenges posed by the erratic climate.

It has emerged that responding to the contextual and dynamic reality of the farming communities is essential. The report also showed that there is a need to strengthen the quality of the existing agro-advisory services considering the socio-economic characteristics of the communities and their preferences and useability towards various advisory platforms.

REFERENCES

Acharjee, T. K., van Halsema, G., Ludwig, F., Hellegers, P., Supit, I. (2019). Shifting planting date of Boro rice as a climate change adaptation strategy to reduce water use. *Agric Syst* 168:131-143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agry.2018.11.006>

Agarwal, T., Goel, P.A., Gartaula, H., Rai, M., Bijarniya, D., Rahut, D. B. and Jat, M. L. (2022). Gendered impacts of climate-smart agriculture on household food security and labor migration: insights from Bihar, India, *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, Vol. 14 No. 1, pp. 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-01-2020-0004>

Aryal, J.P., Sapkota, T.B., Khurana, R. *et al.*(2020). Climate change and agriculture in South Asia: adaptation options in smallholder production systems. *Environ Dev Sustain* 22, 5045–5075. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-019-00414-4>

McDonald, A.J., Balwinder-Singh, Keil, A. *et al.* Time management governs climate resilience and productivity in the coupled rice–wheat cropping systems of eastern India. *Nat Food* 3, 542–551 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-022-00549-0>

Chattopadhyay, N. (2011). Climate change and food security in India. In *Climate Change and Food Security in South Asia*; Lal, R., Sivakumar, M.V.K., Faiz, M.A., Rahman, A.H.M.M., Islam, K.R., Eds.; Springer: Berlin, Germany, pp. 129–251

Faure, G., Desjeux, Y., Gasselin, P. (2012). New Challenges in Agricultural Advisory Services from a Research Perspective: A Literature Review, Synthesis and Research Agenda, *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 18:5, 461-492

Gangopadhyay, P.K., Khatri-Chhetri, A., Shirsath, P.B. *et al.* Spatial targeting of ICT-based weather and agro-advisory services for climate risk management in agriculture. *Climatic Change* 154, 241–256 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-019-02426-5>

GOB (2015). State Action Plan on Climate Change: Building Resilience through Development. Available online: <https://moef.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Bihar-State-Action-Plan-on-Climate-Change-2.pdf> (accessed on 10 July 2023)

Haque, T., & Goyal, A. (2021). Access to Institutional Credit by Farmers in Eastern India. *Journal of Asian Development Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2633190X211040622>

Park, A. G., Davis, A. S., McDonald, A. J. (2018). Priorities for wheat intensification in the Eastern Indo-Gangetic Plains. *Glob Food Secur-Agr* 17:1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2018.03.001>

Raghunathan, K., Kannan, S., Quisumbing, A. R., (2019). Can women’s self-help groups improve access to information, decision-making, and agricultural practices? The Indian case. *Agricultural Economics*. 2019; 50:567–580. <https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12510>

Raghuvanshi, R., Raj, S., Bhattacharjee, S. (2018). Climate smart agriculture and advisory services: approaches and implications for future. Discussion Paper 1, Center for Agricultural Extension Innovations, Reforms and Agripreneurship (CAEIRA), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad

Randhawa, R. K., Singh, H., Kang, M. S. (2014). Global warming and its possible impact on agriculture in India. *Adv. Agron.* 123. pp. 65–121

Shah, T., Rajan, A., Rai, G. P., Verma, S., Durga N. (2018). Solar pumps and South Asia's energy-groundwater nexus: exploring implications and reimagining its future. *Environ Res Lett* 13 (11):115003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aae53f>

ParthSarthi, P. & Singh, A. K. (2013). A simple approach about the characteristics of available surface water in Bihar state of India. *Geosciences.* 3 (2): 68-76. 10.5923/j.geo.20130302.05

Singh, B., McDonald, A. J., Kumar, V., Poonia, S. P., Srivastava, A. K., Malik, R. K. (2019). Taking the climate risk out of transplanted and direct seeded rice: insights from dynamic simulation in Eastern India. *Field Crops Res.* 239:92–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2019.05.014>

Sinha, D., Ahmad, N., & Singh, K. M. (2017). Shrinking Net Sown Area: An Analysis of Changing Land Use Pattern in Bihar. *Journal of AgriSearch.* 3(4), p. 238-243. Available at SSRN: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2907238>

Subash, N., Singh, S. S., Priya, N. (2012). Rainfall variability and its impact on change of cropping systems in Bihar. *Indian School of Soil Conservation.* 40 (1). Pp. 33-40.

TCI (Tata-Cornell Institute). (2022). Food, agriculture and nutrition in Bihar: Getting to zero hunger. Cornell University. Ithaca, NY. Accessed from: https://tci.cornell.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/TCI_Report_FAN-Bihar.pdf

Tesfaye, K.; Aggarwal, P.K.; Mequanint, F.; Shirsath, P.B.; Stirling, C.M.; Khatri-Chhetri, A.; Rahut, D.B. (2017). Climate Variability and Change in Bihar, India: Challenges and Opportunities for Sustainable Crop Production. *Sustainability.* 9(11). 1998. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9111998>

Urfels, A., McDonald, A.J., van Halsema, G. *et al.* (2021). Social-ecological analysis of timely rice planting in Eastern India. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-021-00668-1>

Urfels, A., Kai Mausch, Dave Harris, Andrew J. McDonald, Avinash Kishore, Balwinder-Singh, Gerardo van Halsema, Paul C. Struik, Peter Craufurd, Timothy Foster, Vartika Singh, Timothy J. Krupnik (2023). Farm size limits agriculture's poverty reduction potential in Eastern India even with irrigation-led intensification. *Agricultural Systems.* Volume 207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103618>

Sugandha Munshi, Pratima Bhardwaj. 2021. Self -Help Groups- A Catalyst for Empowering Women In Agriculture! *Elementary Education Online*, 20 (1), 5404-5412. [doi:10.17051/ilkonline.2021.01.574](https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2021.01.574)